

Design of a hyperspectral imaging gonioradiometer for appearance characterization

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Abstract: Optical scatter properties of surfaces can be fully described by the aid of the bidirectional scatter distribution function (BSDF). In recent years, many measuring instruments have been reported that measure the BSDF of flat, spatially uniform surfaces. In this paper, an instrument is presented that allows for the determination of the spectral, spatially variant BSDF of non-flat surfaces. To this end, an existing BSDF measurement system was adapted by incorporation of a snapshot hyperspectral camera. The hyperspectral imaging system enables detailed spectral reflectance data collection for each pixel in the acquired image, paving the way to characterize samples with spatially variant reflectance properties. Moreover, since the hyperspectral system uses a plenoptic acquisition method, measurements can be performed on non-flat surfaces. The main characteristics of the refurbished instrument are discussed, considering challenges such as zooming and focusing on three-dimensional objects. Finally, some example measurements are presented to illustrate the capabilities of the instrument.

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1. Introduction

The total appearance of a surface results from the interplay of several optical attributes, such as the color, surface texture and gloss [1,2]. In addition, visual appearance attributes differ between different illumination and observation geometries. A full characterization of the scattering properties of a surface is included in the spectral Bidirectional Scatter Distribution Function (BSDF). This function defines the surface scattering properties of a material in function of illumination and viewing angles [3,4]. The BSDF of a surface is calculated as the ratio between the surface scattered radiance (either reflected: BRDF, or transmitted: BTDF) and the incident illumination irradiance. In this paper, we only focus on the measurement of BRDF. According to the International Commission of Illumination (CIE) [5], the BRDF f_r for a surface element (x_r, y_r) is defined as (1):

$$f_r(\theta_i, \phi_i, \theta_r, \phi_r, x_r, y_r, \lambda) = \frac{dL_r(\theta_r, \phi_r, x_r, y_r, \lambda)}{dE_i(\theta_i, \phi_i, \lambda)} \quad (1)$$

with dL_r being the differential spectral radiance and dE_i the incident differential spectral irradiance on the surface. (θ_r, ϕ_r) and (θ_i, ϕ_i) respectively represent the direction of light, expressed in spherical coordinates, scattered from the surface and incident on the sample.

BSDF measurement setups typically consist of three distinct parts: the illumination system, sample unit and detector. The illumination part typically incorporates a spectral tunable [6,7] or broadband light source (either Xenon [6–9] or tungsten halogen [10]), and projects a collimated light beam on the sample. The sample holder is often combined with a robot arm, while the light source or detector revolves around the sample enabling a multitude of measurement geometries. Finally, whereas in traditional instruments the detector part generally only consists

of a non-imaging system, recently national metrology institutes have incorporated CCD cameras or an imaging luminance measuring device to assess appearance attributes other than color, e.g. surface texture [6]. Some other measurement devices [11–13] employ a commercial Digital Single Lens Reflex (DSLR) camera to measure a large collection of measurement geometries at once. However, in order to obtain spectral information, the illumination system has to be fitted with a spectral tunable filter, filter wheel or monochromator, where each spectral band is captured sequentially in a different image. This scanning principle slows down the measurement process. The use of a snapshot hyperspectral camera enables us to speed up the measurement process.

Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) captures images in which for each pixel, a continuous spectrum is determined. A hyperspectral image is often represented as a hyperspectral datacube, which can be considered as a stack of bandpass images for each different wavelength band. Several types of hyperspectral imagers are available. Traditionally, a scanning principle is used to capture the full hyperspectral datacube, where scanning can be performed either spectrally or spatially. The moving and switching parts of a scanning hyperspectral camera make these type of systems more complicated, and the scanning principle often slows down the measurement process since multiple integration times have to be performed for capturing one hyperspectral image. As an alternative, a wide variety of snapshot HSI systems have been proposed that capture the entire hyperspectral datacube in one single shot [14,15].

We opted to select a commercially available snapshot hyperspectral camera (Cubert Ultris X50), which utilizes the lenslet-filter array principle, for inclusion in our existing BSDF measurement system. It contains an array of 66 spectral filters ($w \times h: 6 \times 11$) in front of the camera sensor, effectively dividing the imaging sensor in regions where different bandpass wavelength slices are recorded. A hyperspectral image can be taken in maximum 10 seconds, which makes it possible to perform High Dynamic Range (HDR) HSI using multiple exposures, while keeping the measurement duration reasonably short (under one minute). The camera uses a full-frame format (36 mm x 24 mm) CMOS sensor with 47.5 MP resolution [16] and the resulting hyperspectral image contains 570×570 spatial pixels for 164 spectral bands. The Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of the snapshot camera's spectral filters is 14 nm, but the factory software subsamples the spectral channels and returns a datacube in intervals of 4 nm, with the wavelength range starting from 350 nm and ending at 1002 nm. The camera's field of view is 35° when focused on infinity but gets slightly smaller when focusing on shorter distances, has a bit depth of 12 bits and the integration time can vary between 0.1 ms and 10 s. It can be configured to measure absolute spectral radiance.

Interestingly, snapshot hyperspectral cameras that include an array of micro-lenses can also be used to capture information about the light field emanating from a scene. Since spatial as well as angular information is provided by the light field, the depth of field of a two-dimensional image can be adjusted after capture. This paves the way for measuring both the reflectance and three-dimensional shape of a sample at the same time.

HSI devices have been successfully utilized in a wide variety of applications. In the field of remote sensing, it has demonstrated high effectiveness in the analysis of soil, vegetation, water resources and other terrestrial features. Other noteworthy applications include medical imaging, food safety inspection and cultural heritage [17–20]. Currently, some hyperspectral three-dimensional imaging systems already exist: Wu et al. developed a snapshot hyperspectral volumetric microscope for examining biological samples, based on a hyperspectral camera which uses a filter array [21]. Feng et al. developed a compressive spectral 3D imager using a computational hyperspectral camera [22]. Yao et al. used deep learning and stereo matching to measure both spectra and distances in a scene [23]. Some other approaches use separate 3D scanners [24,25] or structured light technologies [25]. A small number of studies have been reported investigating the usefulness of hyperspectral cameras in color science [26,27]. Valero et al. proposed a framework to measure the color of effect-coatings with a hyperspectral camera

[28]. The system achieved high accuracy, but the data capture for a single measurement geometry took approximately 40 minutes, caused by multiple calibrations that had to be performed as well as by working with a slower spectral scanning camera.

The goal of this study is to investigate the implementation and appropriateness of a HSI device for conducting spatially variant BRDF (svBRDF) measurements on non-flat surfaces. To this end, an existing, home-built BRDF measurement system [4] has been adapted, incorporating a snapshot hyperspectral camera. Adaptations made to the system are first described, followed by considering the primary challenges to achieve accurate measurements. The quality of the system is evaluated, both for spectral accuracy as for focal adaptation and depth measurement accuracy. Some example measurements are presented to illustrate the versatility of the device. Finally, a conclusion is drawn, summarizing the possibilities of the setup and considering future work.

2. HSI BSDF system: challenges and design

2.1. Original BSDF instrument

A BSDF measurement setup originally built by Leloup et al. in 2008 was used in this study. The system includes a fixed broadband Xenon illumination source, emitting a collimated light beam using a condenser lens and convex mirror. The relatively flat Xenon emission spectrum ensures a good signal-to-noise ratio for all visual wavelengths. The original detector includes a spectrograph and CCD detector mounted on a rotation arm, ensuring spectral acquisition. The rotation arm can be positioned by use of both a horizontal and vertical rotation axis, which enables measurements for both in-plane and out-of-plane geometries [29]. Both rotation axes are controlled with stepper motors which have an angular resolution of 0.001° . The sample compartment includes a sample holder located at the center of the two rotation axes, on which the sample can be mounted and manually aligned with a horizontal translation and rotation stage. A more detailed description of the original setup can be found in Ref. [4].

The remainder of this section describes the adaptations that were made to the system in order to achieve a calibrated, 3D HSI goniometer. Hardware changes to accommodate for better spatial resolution, straylight reduction and a larger illumination area are explained. Then, software adaptations relating to spectral reflectance calibration, high dynamic range imaging, depth focusing and depth measurement are described.

2.2. Spatial resolution

The aforementioned snapshot hyperspectral camera was incorporated into the described BSDF system in order to measure the svBRDF. Yet, a disadvantage of the snapshot HSI system compared to many scanning hyperspectral cameras is its lower resolution. Consider a snapshot camera and a scanning camera that underneath use the same imaging sensor: the scanning camera uses the full resolution of this sensor multiple times during the scanning process to construct the datacube, while the snapshot system performs only one integration period, resulting in a lower resolution. The spatial resolution can be calculated as the ratio between the image height at the sample and the number of pixels. At the camera's shortest focusing distance for which the camera software is calibrated, i.e., 0.5 m, the spatial resolution equals $553 \mu\text{m}$. This is insufficient for capturing specific visual appearance effects originating from the sample's texture, like orange peel [30] and sparkle [8]. Therefore, to achieve a better spatial resolution, a simple, single-element convex lens with a measured focal length of 18.8 cm was placed in front of the camera (see Fig. 1), allowing the camera to be placed closer to the sample and therefore improving the spatial resolution. Using the thin lens equation with a lens focal length (f) of 18.8 cm, it is calculated that the camera's focusing range now spans from 13.6 cm to 18.8 cm (see Fig. 2). By measuring the sample width in the hyperspectral image at the maximum and minimum object distance, the improved spatial resolution was measured to be respectively $208 \mu\text{m}$ at the maximum object distance of 18.8 cm,

and $143\ \mu\text{m}$ at the minimum object distance, equaling $13.6\ \text{cm}$. Between these distance limits, the spatial resolution will vary linearly.

Fig. 1. Schematic ($45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry) and image of the HSI goniometer.

Fig. 2. Left (a): ray diagram for the convex lens with a focal length of $188\ \text{mm}$. Object A is located at $136\ \text{mm}$ and A' represents its image at $500\ \text{mm}$. Object B is located at a distance of $188\ \text{mm}$ from the lens, with its image laying at infinity. Right (b): distance relationship for the convex lens, calculated with the thin lens equation. Image distances larger than $6000\ \text{mm}$ are capped of, since longer distances can be approximated by infinity. Black markers represent the standard export distances used by the distance focusing algorithm.

Adding a focusing lens improves the spatial resolution significantly; from $553\ \mu\text{m}$ to $143\ \mu\text{m}$. Yet alternative imaging systems summarized in the introduction still achieve better results with spatial resolutions ranging between $24\ \mu\text{m}$ and $45\ \mu\text{m}$. In result, not all visual appearance effects (e.g., sparkle) can be measured with the current system. However, for most visual appearance effects, we expect the current spatial resolution to be sufficient. One such example is the measurement of orange peel [30], as illustrated in the example section.

Further increase of the spatial resolution could be obtained by using a lens with smaller focal length. However, this lens should then be positioned closer to the sample under test. Furthermore, to be used in combination with the hyperspectral snapshot camera, the lens diameter must be larger than the size of the filter array of the camera. Indeed, only under this condition a sharp image is obtained for each wavelength. In result, for the same lens diameter, a smaller distance between lens and sample will lead to a larger obstruction angle of the collimated incident light

beam. The adopted lens with diameter of 8.7 cm and focal length of 18.8 cm results in a relatively large obstruction angle of approximately 25° (Fig. 3(a)).

Fig. 3. Disadvantages of positioning the hyperspectral camera close to the sample. (a) Depiction of the obstruction angle caused by the focusing lens and of the maximum angular deviation due to filters incorporated off-axis in the hyperspectral camera. While the center wavelength filter is aligned on axis, the outer filter is shifted 7.5° off axis. (b) Effect of adding a ND8 filter on interreflections and straylight, shown on a cropped normalized luminance image, reconstructed from the hyperspectral datacube. The blue lines indicate the horizontal intersections of which the relative luminances are plotted below.

2.3. Straylight

Apart from the increased obstruction angle, a second undesirable effect arises by introducing a lens to enhance the spatial resolution. The spectral filters used in the hyperspectral camera are reflective interference filters. They reflect part of the incident light that, in combination with the relatively short distance between the interference filters and the introduced lens, results in additional straylight (see Fig. 3(b)). The resulting interreflections may however be minimized by introducing an absorbing neutral density (ND8) filter between the sample and focusing lens. Measurements and calculations depicted in Fig. 3(b) show that the oscillations caused by the filters are reduced with an average factor of three by including the ND8 filter. To avoid Fresnel reflections, the neutral density filter was tilted with respect to the principal axis.

The question might arise whether the introduction of this ND filter neutralizes the snapshot advantage because the light collection efficiency gets reduced by a factor of 8. While it is difficult to make a hard claim on whether or not this is the case we, to the best of our knowledge, are not aware of any scanning cameras that could rival the speed of the snapshot camera without increasing the illuminance on the sample. We also offer the following reasoning considering the light gathering efficiency in function of integration period. A spectral scanning camera using filters will unavoidably be less efficient than the snapshot camera, as the snapshot camera uses all spectral filters at the same time. Even when considering that for a different camera the ND8 filter could be omitted, the spectral scanning camera would be able to gather 8 spectral bands while the snapshot camera captures all 66 spectral bands in the same time period. In the case of a line scanning camera, the exact efficiencies of the snapshot camera have to be studied in more detail. The spectral filters used in the snapshot camera are at least 90% efficient with a near-vertical slope around their FWHM of 14 nm. Therefore, we argue that a linescan camera that would

contain a dispersive element of 100% efficiency would be able to scan one line 1.1 times more efficiently, and taken into account the advantage of removing the ND filter, 8.8 times faster than the snapshot hyperspectral camera. However, the line scan camera has to scan 570 lines in order to match the same amount of spatial lines, ultimately making it slower than the snapshot camera.

Positioning the camera closer to the sample has a third disadvantage: the angular resolution of the viewing geometry decreases. Only the spectral filter in the middle of the camera is aligned on axis. For filters located off-axis, the viewing direction is shifted. The worst condition occurs for the outer filters on the sensor when focusing on the closest object distance of 13.6 cm. Since the outer filters are approximately 1.8 cm off-center, the resulting angular deviation is 7.5° (Fig. 3(a)).

2.4. Incident beam uniformity

In the original setup an illumination spot of about 2 cm diameter is obtained by projecting a small aperture, positioned in front of the Xe source, onto the sample. In order to enlarge the illumination spot size to a diameter of 4 cm, a diaphragm with larger aperture was introduced into the system. Unfortunately this adjustment introduces additional chromatic aberrations, affecting the uniformity of the illumination spot and causing a color shift towards the edges. This could be improved by including additional optical elements in the illumination path, such as a fly-eye homogenizer.

However, a non-uniform illumination is not an issue when measuring spectral reflectance using a white reference tile with known spectral radiance factor, since the spatial variations in the illumination spot are also observed on the white reference sample [31,32]. To this end, a white reference sample with known spectral reflectance factor (β) values for different measurement geometries was used. The spectral reflectance factor β is defined as:

$$\beta(\lambda) = f_{r,white}(\lambda) \cdot \pi \quad (2)$$

with $f_{r,white}$ the spectral BRDF value.

By measuring the spectral radiance of the calibration tile with the hyperspectral camera, the spectral irradiance incident on the sample can be calculated according to:

$$dE_i(\theta_i, \phi_i, x_r, y_r, \lambda) = \frac{dL_r(\theta_r, \phi_r, x_r, y_r, \lambda)}{f_{r,white}(\lambda)} \quad (3)$$

In result, combining Eqs. 1 to 3, the practical formula for calculating the spectral BRDF of a sample becomes:

$$f_{r,sample} = \frac{dL_{r,sample}(\theta_r, \phi_r, x_r, y_r, \lambda)}{dL_{r,white}(\theta_r, \phi_r, x_r, y_r, \lambda)} \cdot \frac{\beta(\theta_r, \phi_r, \lambda)}{\pi} \quad (4)$$

From Eq. (4), it can be observed that two measurements are needed when measuring the BRDF value of a test sample: one radiance image of the white reference ($dL_{r,white}$), and one radiance image of the test sample ($dL_{r,sample}$). These measurements can be accurately performed, also with inhomogeneous illumination, as long as the colour shifted illumination still contains the full visible spectrum (broadband illumination). This was verified to be the case.

The worst conditions with respect to uniformity of the illumination spot occur at the edges of the spot. A colorimetric CIE XYZ image of the white calibration tile under the $45^\circ:0^\circ$ (illumination angle:viewing angle) geometry was captured, using a TechnoTeam LMK imaging luminance measurement device (ILMD camera). The results are illustrated in Fig. 4, where in the left image the colour shift of the illumination as observed on the white reference is presented in a CIE x,y chromaticity diagram. In the center image the luminance profile is reported of a horizontal intersection, taken from the luminance image of which an RGB preview is depicted in the right image. Broadband illumination is still present at the edges, but a single exposure hyperspectral image of the edges will result in an important amount of noise because of the weaker signal strength. This issue can be countered by implementing HDR imaging using multiple exposures.

Fig. 4. ILMD measurement of the illumination spot. Left: all CIE xy coordinates calculated from the illumination spot, plotted on a chromaticity diagram. Center: horizontal intersection of the luminance, where the red dotted line on the RGB image on the right indicates the location of this intersection.

2.5. HDR

An HDR algorithm was implemented, starting from an image acquisition at the highest possible integration time which can be adjusted according to the sample characteristics. Subsequently, images are acquired with half of the previous integration time, ensuring that in the end, every pixel reports at least 50% of the maximum value for one of the hyperspectral images in the HDR series. Per pixel, reconstruction of the hyperspectral image is performed by selecting the hyperspectral image from the HDR series for which the maximum value of the pixels' spectrum is not saturated. In practice, the HDR algorithm starts with an integration period of 5 seconds and ends at 1 millisecond, which implies 13 iterations. However, the initial and final integration time can be changed easily. Crucially, the HDR stitching is only valid when the camera's response is linear in function of integration time. Linearity for this series of integration times was therefore checked, with the results reporting deviations from linearity smaller than 0.5%.

2.6. Focusing

The lenslet-filter array of the hyperspectral camera causes each wavelength image to be shifted in a slightly different way in comparison to the center image of the camera. No additional lens is needed for focusing on distances between 0.5 m and infinity. Instead, focusing is performed in software by correctly aligning the different wavelength images with each other, since for different distances the spatial shift between the wavelength images differs. The camera is factory-calibrated such that an image distance can be specified on which the hyperspectral image will be focused. The principle where multiple two-dimensional images from different perspectives are recorded, is often called "integral imaging", effectively enabling the measurement of depth [22] as the distance information is encoded in the amount of shift between the different images. This principle makes the camera a lightfield camera, enabling software refocusing on a different distance after the image was taken by re-aligning the wavelength images with different shifts.

By default, only a single image distance corresponding to a specific object distance can be set for the entire image. This means that only flat samples laying perpendicular to the viewing direction are entirely in focus after the factory software alignment. If the calibrated distance does not correspond to the actual distance, significant deformations can be observed in the measured spectra, this effect becoming more important as the object distance gets shorter. Therefore, a robust distance calibration algorithm which achieves a correct focus for each part of the hyperspectral image was developed and implemented. The algorithm first recalibrates the entire original image on a discrete set of distances, and determines for each distance which local parts of the image are in focus. These local parts are then stitched together. A practical example is presented in Fig. 5. The input consists of a hyperspectral image of a three-dimensional cylindrical

object covered with a checkerboard pattern (Fig. 5(a)). The original image is recalibrated for other distances and exported (Fig. 5(b)). In order to examine the sharpness in each reconstructed image, the standard deviation of the luminance is calculated as a metric of contrast. Indeed, where the standard deviation of luminance is highest, the largest difference between the black and white patches is observed, resulting in the highest contrast (see the red tiles in Fig. 5(c)). To determine the contrast based on the standard deviation of luminance, each assessed region of interest must contain at least one edge. This criterion is guaranteed when the region size is larger than the size of one black or white tile of the checkerboard pattern. The final step in the algorithm consists of stitching the sharp regions together (Fig. 5(d)). Note that in the resulting image, the left part exhibits a yellow hue. This results from the non-uniform illumination spot as discussed earlier, caused by increasing the illumination spot size of the system.

Fig. 5. Operating principle of the distance focusing algorithm. The checkerboard pattern is applied to a cylindrical shape, with a measurement geometry of $45^{\circ}:0^{\circ}$ (illumination:viewing), the camera being positioned at 0.5 m from the cylinder's closest point.

The focusing method was originally designed for general use of the hyperspectral camera, when it was not yet mounted on the goniometer system. It also assumed that a checkerboard pattern could easily be applied to the surface of objects. To make the focusing procedure more practical, the BSDF illumination system was fitted with a simple 3D-printed grid that could project a checkerboard pattern on the sample. Since the illumination beam is almost perfectly collimated, the pattern of the grid should be maintained at the location of the sample.

Remark that the implemented algorithm returns distances from 500 mm to infinity. However, due to the introduction of a lens into the system to improve the spatial resolution, the real object distance does no longer correspond to the reported focusing distance. Recalculation of the actual distances between the introduced lens and the object is therefore performed, using the thin lens formula. Moreover, it should also be remarked that due to the thin lens equation, an image distance (d_i) closer to the shortest allowed image distance of 500 mm will cover more actual (object) distances (d_o) than image distances closer to 6000 mm (Fig. 2(b)). Therefore, while the algorithm is exporting to different focus distances, smaller steps have to be taken the closer it goes to 500 mm in order to get an even depth resolution.

2.7. System architecture summary

A non-exhaustive list of specifications of the designed system is presented in Table 1. Depending on the object distance, the spatial resolution and camera collection angle vary. In addition, we opted to select a measurement area of 35 mm in order to stay clear from the Xenon illumination system's border zone, which has a diameter of 40 mm. Some other relevant specifications are also included in the table.

Table 1. Key specifications of the designed HSI goniometer

Object distance	136–188 mm	Camera spectral resolution	14 nm FWHM
Camera spatial resolution	143–208 μm	Light source type	Xenon
Collection full angle	11° - 15°	Size of illuminated area	40 × 40 mm
Light source full angle	1.2°	Measurement area	35 × 35 mm

3. Validation

3.1. Spectral reflectance

In order to validate the spectral precision of the system, spectral reflectance measurements on a Gretag Macbeth ColorChecker (Xrite colorchecker classic, 2017 edition) were put forward to validate the entire measurement setup. Thereby, a 45°:0° measurement geometry was used, while equivalent measurements were also recorded with a portable, commercially available spectrophotometer (Xrite MA T6). Since the purpose is to measure non-uniform colour samples, a fixed integration time was chosen for the measurement of all different samples (hues), for which the recorded signal of the brightest patch (white patch 19) was still not saturated. In practice, the spectral reflectance of each sample was measured separately due to the limited Xe illumination spot size in the BSDF setup. However, the use of a constant integration time makes it possible to consider the spectral reflectance distributions as if they were simultaneously captured in one hyperspectral image of the entire colorchecker.

The white patch (patch 19) of the colorchecker was used as the white reference tile. Additionally, a second HSI measurement was performed outside of the goniometer setup, again in a 45°:0° measurement geometry. For this, a halogen light source was used to illuminate the colorchecker from an incident angle of 45°, while the hyperspectral camera was positioned orthogonal to the sample, at a distance of 0.5 m. Remark that in this setup, which will be denoted further as the ‘halogen setup’, the HSI camera was used without the additional lens and ND filter that needed to be introduced in the BSDF setup. The same processing workflow for all measurements was used for consistency. However, for the halogen setup, an extra, large white reference tile was used that covers the whole colorchecker surface area, in order to cancel out spatial variations of the illumination spot. Indeed, the halogen spot does not allow uniform illumination of the entire test surface.

The spectra obtained from the measurements in the goniometer system, the halogen setup and by use of the conventional portable device, can be found in [Supplement 1](#) (Fig. S1). By way of comparison, the Normalized Mean Error (NME) was calculated as defined in Eq. (5), where S_{phot} and S_{HSI} respectively represent the spectral signal of the test sample as obtained with the spectrophotometer and the hyperspectral camera, where n represents the number of spectral bands. To enable a comparison, the spectra were linearly interpolated to 1 nm wavelength intervals ($n = 300$). In addition, dE_{00} colour differences (CIE 2° Standard Observer, Standard Illuminant D65) were calculated between all data, resp. obtained with the HSI goniometer and the portable spectrophotometer. Crucially, the comparison was performed in the 400 nm – 700 nm wavelength region, in accordance to the Xrite MA T6’s wavelength range.

$$NME = \sum_{\lambda=400}^{700} \frac{|S_{\text{phot}}(\lambda) - S_{\text{HSI}}(\lambda)|}{S_{\text{phot}}(\lambda) \cdot n} \cdot 100 [\%] \quad (5)$$

A similar comparison was performed between the data obtained in the ‘halogen setup’ and the X-Rite portable spectrophotometer. Comparing the results between the BSDF setup and portable spectrophotometer, the average dE_{00} colour difference numbers 1.3, as reported in [Table 2](#). In contrast, for the results obtained in the ‘halogen setup’, this colour difference increases to 1.9. Considering the HSI goniometer system, the best agreement is obtained for the bluish green

hue (patch 6), while the worst agreement is obtained for the dark grey hue (patch 23), likely the result of the low signal to noise ratio for dark colours. A clear overshoot of the measured reflectance for short wavelengths (below 425 nm) can be observed, which is likely caused by a low sensor response for these wavelengths, as well as a non-ideal white reference tile which shows low reflectance values for these short wavelengths. Considering the halogen setup, the best agreement is achieved for the bright green hue (patch 11), while the worst match is achieved for the black patch (patch 24).

Table 2. Comparison of spectral measurements from the setups against a commercially available spectrophotometer

Metric	HSI goniometer		halogen setup	
	NME	dE ₀₀	NME	dE ₀₀
Average	5.1	1.3	6.7	1.9
Median	4.2	1.1	5.9	1.3
Std	3.3	0.7	5.4	2.0
Max	14.2	1.08	26.2	10.3
Min	0.5	1.29	0.7	0.3

3.2. HDR

To improve the measurement accuracy for non-uniform samples for which the integration time cannot be adjusted to achieve a good signal-to-noise ratio for each pixel, an HDR algorithm is proposed, as described earlier. The added value of implementing this HDR algorithm is illustrated with measurements on all 24 samples of the Gretag Macbeth ColorChecker, using the halogen-based setup described in the previous section. First, a series of 20 hyperspectral measurements was taken with a constant integration time of 1.8 s, determined from the maximum signal below saturation for the sample with the highest spectral reflectance (white sample, patch 19). In a second stage, the measurement was repeated, yet implementing the HDR algorithm, which means that the integration time was adjusted to ensure that every spatial pixel reports at least 50% for its brightest wavelength of the maximum value for one of the hyperspectral images in the HDR series. These measurements were again compared to measurements from the Xrite MA T6.

The mean dE₀₀ color difference for all 24 samples, between the 20 averaged HSI camera measurements with constant integration time (no HDR) and the Xrite MA T6, numbers 1.9. This result is similar to the resulting average color difference for a single frame image as reported in Table 2. Hence, there is no meaningful improvement when just averaging multiple image captures.

When using the HDR algorithm on the other hand, the mean dE₀₀ color difference for all 24 patches, as compared to the results obtained with the Xrite MA T6, is reduced to 1.1. This corresponds to an average improvement of 0.8 units. Logically, the largest improvement are encountered for dark patches (Fig. 6), for which the signal to noise ratio improves the most. For a select number of patches (patches 6, 11 and 16), the color difference slightly increases when using the HDR algorithm. We suspect this is caused by some small deviations in the linearity from the sensor, for which we were unable to correct. However, these restricted inferior results are negligible in comparison to the largely improved correspondence for all other color patches. In general, we can thus consider the HDR procedure to improve the measurement accuracy.

Fig. 6. Comparison of dE_{00} between the Xrite MA T6 measurements and averaging or HDR results.

3.3. Depth focusing

Different methods can be put forward to check the suitability of the developed 3D depth focusing algorithm. First, the checkerboard pattern, a projection of which is used in the practical implementation of the algorithm, may also be printed on a flat cardboard which is then tilted under a certain angle with respect to the HSI camera. After refocusing, it is expected that the spectral reflectance distribution of the white patches corresponds to the reflectance spectra when viewed perpendicularly. Without refocusing, on the contrary, some wavelengths appear as large peaks or gaps in the spectrum, caused by a wrong amount of shifting of that specific wavelength image. A practical example is provided in Fig. 7. Although the focusing algorithm improves the

Fig. 7. Focusing on a tilted checkerboard and Gretag Macbeth chart. The center of the red square indicates the pixel from which the reflectance spectra are shown.

spectral reflectance distribution significantly, small oscillations may still be observed. This effect only appears for very small focusing zones, driving the focus detection algorithm as well as the factory distance calibrations to its limits. However, these small fluctuations could be removed with appropriate lowpass filtering. When evaluating the same effect on the edge of a sample of the Gretag Macbeth ColorChecker, it is observed that the spectral reflectance distribution is reconstructed without large oscillations.

A second assessment of the depth algorithm was performed on non-flat objects. In Fig. 8 (column a and b, upper row a), an image is depicted of a flat cardboard and a cylindrical object, resp., on which a checkerboard pattern is projected. A horizontal intersection of the resulting shape, retrieved from the hyperspectral image, is plotted against the real shape (see row c). In Fig. 8 column c, a further distance measurement is presented, performed in the HSI goniometer setup on a coffee cup. This clearly illustrates the possibility to measure distances by projecting a checkerboard pattern on the shape. However, the tiles of the projected checkerboard are not as small and sharp as with the physical checkerboard, which is caused by limitations of the 3D printer used to print the raster, as well as by the illumination not being perfectly collimated. This ultimately leads to a less detailed depth measurement: at column c, row c, the pattern of the checkerboard was too big to accurately check the focus, resulting in holes shaped like the checkerboard pattern to appear. In the future, this issue will be solved by utilizing a more precise projection method.

A final test was performed to check the importance of the window size used in the focusing algorithm. Therefore, the window size was adjusted to different surface areas of the checkerboard pattern that is projected on the cylindrical shape (coffee cup). The window size is indicated as a

Fig. 8. Examples of distance measurements made by the HSI camera, the red box in row a indicates the scanned zone shown on the distance images. Orientations for the 3D plots were chosen to best show the measured curve, and therefore do not match the orientations of the distance images. Also note that, for the cylinder (column b), the scaling of the distance axis is not the same as for the X and Y axis. Row c shows horizontal intersections of the measured shapes, compared against the ground truth shapes.

percentage, with 100% indicating that the window area exactly corresponds to the size of one tile of the checkerboard. When the window is too small, not every assessed region contains an edge, which is mandatory for evaluating the sharpness. This results in bad focusing and depth measurement (see Fig. 9(column a)). On the other hand, increasing the window size too much also leads to a less precise focusing and depth measurement, although this effect is limited (Fig. 9(column b)). The optimal window size was found to be 300% (Fig. 9(column c)). Finally, gaussian filtering with a standard deviation of 5 pixels, for the shape determined by the optimal window size, has been applied to filter out irregularities in the distance estimation (Fig. 9(column d)), delivering the best results. It is important to note that the curvature of the object will also influence the shape of the projected checkerboard pattern. A strongly tilted sample for example would smear out the black and white patches of the checkerboard pattern. The absolute window size would then have to be increased to again be 300% of the window size of the patch. In addition, so far only objects with constant curvature were considered. Future work could include non-constant curvatures to further examine the behaviour of the algorithm, for which a variable window size could be a valid alternative.

Fig. 9. Influence of window size and gaussian filtering on distance estimation. Gaussian filtering was performed on the optimal window result, with the standard deviation set to 5 pixels.

4. Practical examples

4.1. Orange peel

The HSI gonioradiometer was tested on its applicability for measuring the orange peel effect. Samples that exhibit orange peel distort reflections in such a way that they resemble an orange peel, which is caused by smooth bidirectional variations in the surface profile [33]. A standard sample set of ACT orange peel test samples was measured, which contains ten black samples with an orange peel rating from 1 to 10. The measurement procedure as described by Sone and Watanabe [30] was largely followed, where the same type of ACT test samples was used for validation. The described method projects a line onto the sample, which we implemented by placing a rectangular aperture, covered by a diffuser, in between the illumination path. The HSI camera focusses on the virtual image of this aperture, and a luminance image. In our setup, focusing on the virtual image was impossible, since the focusing distance now not only includes the distance from the camera to the sample, but it also includes the distance between the sample and the rectangular source, which ultimately causes the total focusing distance to be larger than

18.8 cm. Therefore, only one wavelength image was used, since separate wavelength images are still sharp because it is mainly the spatial shift between different wavelength slices that introduce blur. For the wavelength slice of 470 nm, the sensor's response in combination with the spectral characteristics of the illumination and sample was the highest, leading to the best signal-to-noise ratio. An illustration of the blurred L^* image and the sharper wavelength slice is presented in Fig. 10. Since the samples are achromatic and have no differences between them, other than the orange peel effect, it does not matter that a wavelength image is used instead of the L^* image.

Fig. 10. Top: preview image of the ACT orange peel samples (middle range: rank 2–7). Bottom: L^* image compared to the wavelength slice with a center wavelength of 470 nm.

The workflow is graphically presented in Fig. 11. The input L^* image is used to construct a binary image by thresholding. The reference paper does not state the used threshold value. We expect a logical value to be 50% of the maximum intensity, or that histogram-based global intensity thresholding was used (Otsu's method). In our case, these methods caused finer texture details to be lost. Therefore, an optimized threshold value of 10% was used. This value was manually selected by evaluating different binary images with different thresholds, and choosing the one where the orange peel line was the clearest. Further research could improve the sharpness of the L^* image, which on its turn could allow for a threshold value of 50%. However, this is out of the scope of the current research.

From the binary image, the deviation between a straight fit of the projected line and the distorted edge caused by the orange peel effect is determined. Next, this deviation is transformed using the Fast Fourier transform to the spatial frequency distribution, and is then integrated by the visual transfer function of the human eye. This results in an "orange peel noise" rating. In order to transform the orange peel noise to the orange peel ranking from the sample set, the reference paper authors [30] fit a logarithmic function to the orange peel noise, after which the correlation with the ACT sample set can be determined. Using this method, a Pearson correlation coefficient R^2 of 0.97 was achieved, similar to the reference paper's results where the Pearson correlation also numbered 0.97.

Fig. 11. Orange peel measurement procedure. P_1 and p_2 are used to fit the logarithmic function to the correct scaling: $P_1 = 6.29$, $p_2 = -38.68$.

4.2. Curved samples

Instead of measuring one viewing geometry at a time, the HSI gonioradiometer can measure a curved object that includes a high amount of different measurement geometries (combinations of lighting and viewing angles). With the 3D measurement capabilities, it is possible to derive the angles of the geometries by taking the arctangent of the gradient of the measured shape. To test this, a sample consisting of a dark green piece of paper was folded on a 3D-printed curved shape. While it is theoretically possible to perform an extensive calibration with a 3D white reference sample with known shape, we opted to simply apply a white sheet of paper on the same 3D-printed shape in order to speed up the measurement process.

The 3D-printed shape covers an angular range of 60° , with the angle between illumination and camera set to 45° (phase angle). The shape was placed randomly on the sample holder, and a 3D measurement was performed. The resulting illumination geometries were measured to range from 5° to 65° , while the viewing angles range from -40° till 20° . Accurate angle estimation is only possible when the measured 3D shape shows no abrupt changes or irregularities. Therefore, lowpass filtering (first order savgol filter with window size 10) was applied to the measured 3D shape.

Colorimetric CIELAB coordinates were calculated in combination with CIE D65 illuminant and the 2° Standard Observer. The reflectance of the white reference paper was measured with the Xrite MA T6 spectrophotometer under $45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry, which then allows for a correction of the non-perfect reference white by multiplying the green paper's reflectance spectrum with this white paper spectrum.

For comparison, the green paper was measured in a $45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry with the spectrophotometer as well, reporting CIELAB Lab color coordinates of (37.16,-5.35,-0.41). The calculated CIELAB

color coordinates with the HSI gonioradiometer, in all measurement geometries are presented graphically in Fig. 12. A clear color shift is observed in relation to the measurement geometry. For $45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry, CIELAB values number (37.4,-7.3,-0.6), although there is a shift at the $45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry which leads to a measurement uncertainty. In comparison to the Xrite MA T6 measurement results, a dE_{00} color difference of 2.24 is obtained. This difference is larger than in our previous tests on the Gretag Macbeth chart, likely caused by the fact that now, the accuracy of the measurement also depends on the accuracy of the geometry measurement. Therefore, we believe that the reported difference is still an acceptable result.

Fig. 12. Measurement results on a curved sample. Part a illustrates the 3D shape and the viewing geometry. In the shown configuration, both angles are positive. When α_{view} shifts to the other side of the normal, the angle becomes negative. Part b illustrates measurement results, where colorimetric calculations were performed for CIE D65 and 2° standard observer conditions.

4.3. Non-uniform sample

As a final example, a measurement under the $45^\circ:0^\circ$ geometry of a wooden floor tile is shown in Fig. 13. The tile is composed of multiple wood elements that additionally contain woodgrain texture. This texture introduces strongly angle-dependent reflections which would alter the true background color measurement of the wood. The hyperspectral imaging systems allows for a local determination of the spectral reflectance on a non-textured part of the tile. A non-imaging BRDF measurement device would not be able to distinguish between the different wood panels and textured zones.

Fig. 13. Measurement of a wooden floor tile. The background reflectance of the wood patch in the upper right corner is darker than the background reflectance of the wood patch in the lower right corner.

5. Conclusion

A new HSI gonioradiometer was designed and verified, intended for measuring a broad range of visual appearance characteristics. The inclusion of a hyperspectral camera into an existing non-imaging gonioradiometer enables the measurement of spectral reflectance properties and their spatially variant BRDF. One of the main benefits of using a snapshot hyperspectral camera is that measurements can be performed rather quickly and with a high dynamic range. The main disadvantage, however, is the limited spatial resolution in comparison to hyperspectral scanning cameras. Nonetheless, in this study we propose a method to improve the spatial resolution while minimizing stray light through the introduction of respectively a lens and an ND filter in the optical path. Alternatively, by modifying the illumination path, a checkerboard pattern can be projected onto a uniform sample. By exploiting the lightfield capabilities of the camera, it is then possible to measure 3D shapes, making the setup more versatile. Finally, while the HSI gonioradiometer is primarily designed to measure visual appearance attributes, the setup could be used for other research purposes as well. Examples include digitizing small archaeological objects or examining art pieces.

Future research will focus on implementing more visual appearance measurement procedures using the setup. In addition, comparative measurements will be performed to investigate the correspondence of results with similar devices at other measurement facilities. The 3D measurement capabilities will be further explored and refined. In addition, the addition of a better lens in the form of an achromatic doublet which is also coated with anti-reflective coatings would reduce both chromatic aberrations and stray light. A more advanced, multi-element lens system could also be designed in order to achieve a better spatial resolution, while also increasing the angular resolution by mounting the camera further from the sample.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request.

Supplemental document. See [Supplement 1](#) for supporting content.

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